

Workshop summary:

Advancing Collaboration and Data Sharing Agreements in Biomedical AI Research Workshop

Wednesday 4th February 2026

Overview

The Advancing Management Skills in Biomedical AI Research Project started on 1st October 2025 and has been a rapid research project investigating difficulties in cross-sector collaboration and data sharing for Biomedical AI research. To address this question, it was essential to engage a broad range of stakeholders working in Biomedical AI research so that we could gain a better understanding of current challenges and barriers, surface existing best practices and ongoing initiatives and move towards practical and innovative solutions.

We started by forming a working group to begin understanding the challenges and to get suggestions on the structure and focus of our workshop. Therefore, informed by input from our working group, we organised a one-day in person workshop (Advancing Collaboration and Data Sharing Agreements in Biomedical AI Research Workshop) that was held on 4th February 2026 at Wallacespace in Spitalfields, London.

We brought together a wide range of stakeholders from different sectors, different disciplines and roles within the AI biomedical research community, including the biomedical data science community, research technical professional networks, and research infrastructures. These included individuals working across the management of AI research such as legal, research and strategy managers, knowledge exchange and research culture professionals, as well as data science and AI specialists.

The workshop was designed to enable knowledge exchange and networking, capture in-depth information about challenges from different perspectives, and give space for creative design of innovative practical solutions.

This workshop was invite only. In total, 114 people were invited from a curated list of identified individuals relevant to our research question. This included those that had previously signed up for our working group through our direct emails and our open call for working group participants. 45 people registered and 39 attended the workshop. They represented 23 organisations of which there were Universities, Independent Research Organisations, Research Funders, Charities, Research Infrastructures, Health Data providers/controllers, Industry, Patients and Healthcare providers. A list of names, organisations and roles of attendees can be found in appendix 1 at the end of this document.

Resources and outputs produced:

- **Presentation slides and workshop templates** - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18498196>
- **Workshop filled in worksheets** - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19888321>
- **Scriberia illustrations from workshop** - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19889219>

Approach to knowledge exchange and promoting accessibility

When bringing together a diverse group that has not previously interacted, it is important to create the right environment for knowledge exchange and networking on the day. We therefore had to think carefully about the venue and schedule for the workshop. We selected a venue that provided comfortable surroundings, a casual rather than a formal environment and good food. We set up the room in tables of 6 people to promote interaction, and ensured the groups were a mix of people from different organisations. We kept space in the schedule for breaks to enable networking – we actively encouraged and asked participants to meet new people at breakfast, coffee and lunch breaks.

We made available and promoted accessibility funds within event invitations and on our registration form to make the event more accessible to those that often do not have funds to travel to events. This is particularly important to those defined as research support staff or professional services staff as their input is necessary to get an accurate understanding of this topic. They usually do not have funds available to attend events or join in research of this nature meaning that outputs can be biased towards researcher only viewpoints.

We decided to keep the event as in person only so that we could have everyone present in the room together making interactions easier and we purposefully made activities paper based to remove the distractions that can occur when attendees have laptops in front of them.

We aimed to have a diverse range of organisations represented (different sectors and types of organisations), and we also intentionally invited a diverse range of people in terms of gender, age, career stage and ethnic background.

Morning activities

As attendees entered the workshop, we invited them to choose a character. These fantasy characters were based on the roles and personas we had identified during the development of the working group and the event. This focus on ensuring diverse perspectives and input from key stakeholders in this area, particularly different job roles that are part of Biomedical AI research teams, was important for gathering balanced points of view. We felt it particularly important to get input from people in operational roles that are usually not included in research. See slide 2 of the workshop presentation to see the characters and personas as well as the illustrations by Scriberia.

For the morning activities, attendees were assigned to pre-determined groups based on job roles and a mix of different organisations. There were seven groups and every group had a facilitator from the ABDC team or The Alan Turing Institute.

The workshop activities started with an introduction to the agenda for the day and the aims and objectives of our wider project - Advancing Biomedical Data Science Careers (ABDC) - by Project Lead, Emma Karoune. Then, we heard from Giulia Tomba, Senior Research Associate, about the Advancing Management Skills in Biomedical AI Research project – the focus of the event. She gave a brief presentation of the challenges found in the project working group and introduced the aims of the day, which were to identify barriers, document best practices, and recommend innovative solutions.

Activity 1: Imagining Utopia

Our first activity was 'Imagining Utopia' - an activity designed to allow attendees to think creatively to begin with. Attendees were asked to think about the following statement:

'It's 5-10 years from now. Your team has just signed the perfect data sharing and collaboration agreements for biomedical AI research.'

The groups had 40 minutes to discuss and write notes together. They also had several prompts on our presentation slides:

Step 1: Individual reflection

Write down keywords and short phrases.

Step 2: Group discussion

- What does success look like in practice?
- What makes this work?
- Who is involved and who benefits the most?
- We provided a structured worksheet that participants could write on or stick post-it notes.

All worksheets provided to attendees at the workshop can be found in appendix 2.

Activity 2: Challenge Mapping

After a coffee break, Giulia introduced activity 2, which aimed to get participants to address one of the challenges identified by our working group. We assigned challenges to the groups based on the roles we thought were most relevant to the challenge. The participants were asked to map their given challenge to the AI lifecycle and discuss the causes and how it should be addressed.

The AI lifecycle image and challenge sheets can be found in appendix 3 and 4.

Afternoon activities

Lightning presentations

At the beginning of our afternoon session, we had three short lightning talks from relevant current projects.

- **Alex Black and Eden Ruffell, from Moorfield's Eye Hospital**, spoke about the INSIGHT eye hub. This data hub is the world's largest ophthalmic bio-resource of 1.9 million patients with 30+ million eye images linked to clinical records. They spoke about the AI model that has been developed by the INSIGHT team for eye diseases and also how other researchers can access the data and also collaborate with them on AI research.
- **Yemi Macaulay, from Health Data Research UK**, talked about the work of the UK Health Data Research Alliance on standardising data access agreements. They spoke about their process for developing the template and the next steps for implementation and adoption.
- **Luis Santos, from The Alan Turing Institute**, talked about FRIDGE – a technical solution for sharing sensitive data. They spoke about supporting the extension of a client organisation's information governance model to HPC clusters.

Activity 3: Solution Design

The rest of the afternoon session was dedicated to thinking about solutions. During the lunch break, we had asked attendees to sign up for a challenge group (the same challenges from the morning 'Challenge Mapping' activity). They then joined this group to design a solution for the challenge.

The participants were first given 10 minutes to brainstorm and prototype solutions. We encouraged them to think up as many as possible but have 3 as a minimum. Then they were to pitch their ideas to their group and decide which idea to take forward to design in more detail for the rest of the session. They then had about 1 hour to focus on designing their chosen solution.

Sharing designs

At the end of this session, participants were asked to present their solution to the whole group, and we had time to look at the worksheets produced by each group.

The day ended with some informal networking.

Feedback from attendees

100% of respondents to our feedback form said the event was just the right length.

For different activities:

- Imagining Utopia - 25% somewhat useful and 75% useful or extremely useful
- Challenge mapping – 100% useful or extremely useful
- Lightning talks - 100% useful or extremely useful
- Solution design - 100% useful or extremely useful

Selected quotes from participants

What did you like most about the Advancing collaborations and data sharing agreements in the biomedical AI research workshop?

- *Everything!*
- *Networking time (as I will soon be looking for a job!), people organised into groups with similar background/expertise for the morning, great venue and food, engaging discussions.*
- *The diversity of participants with different expertise.*
- *The diversity of stakeholders you brought together - it was very interesting to hear different perspectives and experiences at the table discussions.*

What could have been done differently? Do you have any suggestions on how to improve future events?

- *The morning was quite energised, but the afternoon solution design a bit less so. I don't know if it was because we swapped around groups or because it was harder to design actual solutions. We got a bit derailed and perhaps we could have done with a facilitator to keep us on track.*
- *Maybe add a section where everyone can check the solution design of different group.*
- *There could have been more time spent on reporting back from each table/session, but actually I preferred the way the event was run, so I don't really have suggestions for improvement*

Additional comments

- *I gave an update about the event at our team meeting yesterday and everyone found it really interesting and an important topic!*

Diversity monitoring

29 out of the 45 people registered for our event filled in the diversity monitoring part of the registration form. Not all these individuals responded to all the questions.

- **Age:** The range of ages was 30 to 65. Most attendees were between 30 and 49 (49%); a smaller percentage (11%) were between 50 to 65. 40% of registered individuals did not answer this question.
- **Gender:** Of the 45 registered participants, 46.6% were woman, 15.5% were men and 37.7% did not answer the question.
- **Ethnicity:** Of the 45 registered participants, 42.2% were white, 6.6% any other ethnicity, 4.4% Black, 4.4% Mixed, 4.4% Asian and 37.7% did not answer this question.
- **Caring responsibilities:** Of the 45 registered participants, 26.6% reported having no caring responsibilities, 28.8% were primary or joint carers of a child or children under 18, 4.4% preferred not to say and 40% did not answer this question.
- **Education:** All those that responded to diversity monitoring questions (64.4%), either had an education level of level 7 (master's degree or equivalent) or level 8 (doctorate or equivalent).

Considerations for future events

- Overall, the format worked well – attendees were very enthusiastic and engaged throughout the day.
- Many attendees commented on the quality of the venue and how much they enjoyed the day – good resources, comfortable, informal and great food. We had created a good environment for knowledge exchange.
- We invited the right people – 87% of registered people attended, which is a very high conversion rate from registration to attendance. However, the in-person only format does restrict the number of people that can attend and often restricts people that have to travel longer distances. We did provide an accessibility fund for travel and accommodation costs to try to overcome some travel barriers, but this does not get over the barrier of time or things like caring responsibilities. Ideally, if we were doing a longer project, we would engage with more people in the ecosystem by holding online workshops.
- There was good engagement throughout the workshop, both through written and spoken contributions. Based on some feedback, we might want to have a facilitator with all groups throughout the workshop. We intentionally did not provide facilitators for the afternoon activity to allow everyone to choose the challenges they wanted to work on as we felt people were passionate about certain topics, including members of our team that wanted to contribute to solutions and had acted as facilitators in the morning.
- We could have possibly had more lightning talks as these were popular with attendees and sparked a number of interesting questions.

Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge the contributions of the wider Biomedical AI research community to this event and the overall work of this project. These contributions included being part of and attending working group meetings from October 2025 to December 2025, individual meetings with the research team, asynchronous contributions to working group note documents and attendance at our workshop on 4th February 2026.

The project and event were shaped, organised and facilitated by the ABDC Team, and we also want to thank our Turing colleagues, Vanessa Forster, Kit Good, Luis Santos, Martin O'Reilly, Mark Saunders for their helpful initial discussions on the project topic and their help with facilitation at working group meetings and our workshop.

All illustrations were created by Scriberia with the Advancing Biomedical Data Science Careers Team and workshop attendees. Used under a CC-BY 4.0 licence. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19889219.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Breakdown of attendees by name, organisation and job title (alphabetical by organisation)

Name	Organisation	Job Title
Emma Gordon	Administrative Data Research UK (ADRUK), Economic and Social	Director
Leslie Glass	Cancer Research UK (CRUK)	Data Liaison Manager
Lewis Hotchkiss	Dementia Platform UK	Research Officer
Daria Sokolova	European Molecular Biology Laboratory's - European	Scientific Project Officer
Gabriele Rinck	EMBL-EBI	Project Lead
Kim Gurwitz	EMBL-EBI	Scientific Training Lead (Grants Programme)
Jean-Baptiste Cazier	Francis Crick Institute	Head of Bioinformatics & Biostatistics, and Data Science
Yemi Macaulay	Health Data Research UK (HDRUK)	Information Governance and Research Manager
Sam Rowley	Medical Research Council (MRC)	Programme Manager
Alex Black	Moorfields Eye Hospital	Research Communications Lead
Mario Moroso	National Institute of Health and Care Research (NIHR)	Assistant Director - Research Programmes
Narissa Leyland	NHS England	Head of Data Governance
Sarah Markham	None	Patient
Konstantinos Kaouras	Our Future Health	Data Protection Officer & Legal Counsel
Katherine Tucker	Roche Products Ltd	Expert Data Privacy Technical Lead
Chaimaa Tarzi	Teesside University	Lecturer in Computing and Games
Emma Karoune	The Alan Turing Institute	Principal Researcher
Denise Bianco	The Alan Turing Institute	Senior Research Community Manager

Appendix 1: Breakdown of attendees by name, organisation and job title (alphabetical by organisation), continued.

Name	Organisation	Job Title
Giulia Tomba	The Alan Turing Institute	Senior Research Associate
Martin O'Reilly	The Alan Turing Institute	Director of Research Engineering
Vera Matser	The Alan Turing Institute	Head of Strategic Capabilities
Kit Good	The Alan Turing Institute	Data Protection Manager
Alison Marsh	The Alan Turing Institute	Senior Programme Manager
Luis Santos	The Alan Turing Institute	Principal Data Wrangler
Eirini Koutsouroupa	The Alan Turing Institute	Programme Manager
Sophie Perret	The Alan Turing Institute	Enrichment PhD Student
Kathryn Woodward	The Alan Turing Institute	Enrichment PhD Student
Jaspreet Gill	The George Institute of Global Health, Imperial College London	Women's Health Program Manager
Victoria Yorke-Edwards	University College London (UCL)	Senior Research Data Steward
Michelle Harricharan	University College London (UCL)	Principal Research Data Steward Head of Profession for Data Stewardship
Menghan Cui	University College London (UCL)	UKRI research fellow
Eden Ruffell	University College London (UCL)	PhD Student
Fatemeh Torabi	University of Cambridge	Assistant Professor Healthcare Data Science
Jess Shilton	University of Leeds	Data Scientist in Biomedical Science Careers

Appendix 1: Breakdown of attendees by name, organisation and job title (alphabetical by organisation), continued.

Name	Organisation	Job Title
Rachel Hetherington	University of Oxford	Project Manager
Eva Caamano Gutierrez	University of Liverpool	Director of Computational Biology Facility
Miranda Mourby	University of Sheffield	Researcher in Law
Joe Watts	UK Biobank	Director of Data Policy
Mate Palfy	Wellcome Sanger Institute	Open Science Lead

Appendix 2: Worksheets for workshop activities

Activity 1 - Imagining Utopia
GROUP: _____

A perfect **data sharing** agreement is one that...

This enables:

Something concrete that makes it work

WHO makes this work?

... who benefits the most?

A perfect **collaboration** agreement is one that...

This enables:

Something concrete that makes it work

WHO makes this work?

... who benefits the most?

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Appendix 2: Worksheets for workshop activities, continued.

Activity 2 - Challenge Mapping		Challenge:	GROUP:
What does it cause?			
Lifecycle stage where it appears			
Where should it be addressed?			
Who should address it?			
What is blocking progress?			
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Activity 3 - Solution Design		New Solution name:	GROUP:
Challenge:	Value proposition statement:		
Initial brainstorming of potential solutions:	People and organisations: Who is it targeted at? Who needs to be involved in developing this solution?		
	Details of solution: What, where, how, resources needed, cost, timeframe (short-term or long-term project)		
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Appendix 3: AI lifecycle image for activity 2

Appendix 4: Challenge prompt sheets for activities 2 and 3

Challenge 1: Data access friction, slow project starts and time pressures

Delays and risks in biomedical AI projects arise from complex data access processes, evolving project requirements, and insufficient early planning. Researchers often struggle to scope projects without initial data access, and navigating legal, technical and operational requirements slows progress.

Pressures to start research projects quickly can conflict with the time needed to set up governance, operational structures, risk assessments and data access, potentially creating delays, inefficiencies or even project risks.

What we heard:

in 2025, is it still acceptable to not plan access to data ahead of time?

Within collaborations, some partners may already have access to data, while others may still need to negotiate it.

“Chicken-and-egg” situation where researchers cannot get access to data because their project application is too broad or not detailed enough, but they cannot add the necessary detail without first exploring the data.

As projects evolve, researchers’ data needs may change, leading to repeated access requests and further delays.

Overall project timelines are often too short to accommodate complex regulatory, legal and technical requirements.

Tight timelines and misalignment or priorities can force researchers to use suboptimal

Appendix 4: Challenge prompt sheets for activities 2 and 3, continued.

Challenge 2: Fragmented infrastructure and lack of integrated systems

Researchers face delays and extra work because data systems are fragmented across institutions. Differences in platforms, protocols, metadata standards, and secure compute environments make it hard to access, link, and analyse health data efficiently.

What we heard:

- NHS partners often lack secure compute environments compatible with restrictions*
- To comply with data sharing, researchers need to use fragmented systems, which add extra burden.*
- Lack of all-in-one data sharing infrastructural solution to smoothly integrate systems in universities and the NHS.*
- Different disciplines vary in data and metadata standards (or lack thereof).*

Challenge 3: Risk assessment and governance misalignment

Risk assessment and governance are essential for responsible biomedical AI research, but they are often treated as late-stage or compliance-only tasks. Misalignment between researchers, legal teams, and data custodians can lead to inefficiencies, repeated reviews, and missed opportunities to plan responsibly from the start. AI-specific data concerns, such as re-identification, add further complexity.

What we heard:

- Ethical approval and output control processes are not fully integrated into project planning.*
- Stakeholders lack guidance on embedding governance, risk assessment and public involvement across complex projects.*
- Alignment is needed between research ambitions and legal/data custodians' risk perspectives.*
- Projects sometimes begin before agreements or governance structures are in place, creating risk for researchers, data custodians, and institutions.*
- AI projects using health data carry risks such as re-identification or unintended disclosure.*

Appendix 4: Challenge prompt sheets for activities 2 and 3, continued.

Challenge 4: Cultural and multidisciplinary barriers

Collaboration across roles, disciplines and institutions is complicated by different languages, priorities, incentives and organisational cultures. These barriers can slow research, create misunderstandings, and make alignment on goals and practices more difficult.

What we heard:

Different stakeholders have different priorities, which can create siloes and slow decision-making.

Risk responsibilities are often compartmentalised, so each team acts conservatively within its own scope.

Working across teams is challenging because teams don't always share the same terminology, assumptions and regulatory frameworks.

Some teams treat procedures as administrative tasks rather than meaningful

Challenge 5: AI-specific contractual complexity

Biomedical AI projects often require agreements that balance standard templates with bespoke needs. Standard agreements are easier to process but may not cover AI-specific issues like model ownership, outputs, secondary data use, or commercial sensitivities. Bespoke agreements address these issues but take longer to negotiate, creating tension and potential delays.

What we heard:

Multiple contracts and differing templates create lengthy negotiation processes.

Standard templates may not fully cover AI-specific considerations or be accessible and transparent enough for all collaborators.

Lack of coordination between funders and institutions can create competition for the same datasets, adding complexity to agreements.

Governance around multimodal datasets, especially on post-project secondary use, is still quite unclear.

Appendix 4: Challenge prompt sheets for activities 2 and 3, continued.

Challenge 6: Public trust, engagement and societal acceptance

Biomedical AI projects depend on trust from patients, the public, and regulators. Misunderstandings about AI, insufficient stakeholder involvement, or assumptions about public acceptability can undermine data access, ethical approval, and adoption of research outcomes. Engaging stakeholders early is challenging, especially in multidisciplinary and international contexts.

What we heard:

Public perception of AI can be cautious or fearful, which may affect willingness to share data and engage with research.

Data regulators may adopt a conservative approach if the public or patients are wary of AI, slowing approvals or limiting access to datasets.

Some private-sector partners, focused on rapid development, may be reluctant to engage in public or patient-facing discussions.

Researchers may assume public priorities or benefits without engaging stakeholders meaningfully.

AI is complex and multifaceted, but is often simplistically presented as a single concept, making it difficult to engage meaningfully with the public.

Challenge 7: Skills, training and workforce development

Biomedical AI projects require skilled personnel across multiple domains (AI, data wrangling, legal, ethics, governance, PPIE). There are gaps in training, unclear responsibilities, and insufficient continuity, which slow projects and reduce their effectiveness.

What we heard:

Training is piecemeal; there's no cohesive pathway to prepare researchers for complex projects (e.g., in data management and security).

Roles critical for compliance and data governance may be understaffed or underskilled.

New researchers often don't know where to get guidance or mentorship.

There is a desire for standardised, widely recognised best practice training programmes.